

NAVIGATING LEARNER'S ACTIVITY SHEET EXPERIENCE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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Abstract

The study explored the lived experiences of learners utilizing the Learner's Activity Sheets (LAS) at Samar National School using phenomenological study. The purpose of the study was to find out how grade 10 students used LAS to improve their critical thinking and language skills. The results showed that using LAS significantly enhanced students' critical thinking abilities, participation, and engagement in class activities, as well as their English proficiency. Pupils could get past language-related obstacles, gain self-assurance in their language abilities, and realize their full academic potential. The study also revealed difficulties and restrictions related to the use of LAS, offering insightful information for improving its usefulness in language training. The study answers some questions about how LAS is used in English language classes, mainly in Philippine public high schools.

Keywords: Learner's Activity Sheet (LAS), English language education, language proficiency, critical thinking, student engagement.

Introduction

In the Philippines, English is both a second language and a medium of teaching at the college level. Learner's Activity Sheets (LAS) are now used all over the world in schools (Akhtar & Thomson, 2017). LAS are "structured guides that outline learning objectives, activities, and assessment tasks for students to complete independently or collaboratively" (Merriam, 2020, p. 123). They provide a way for students to learn and be involved. However, the real-life experiences of students navigating LAS are still not well studied.

This study uses qualitative phenomenology to look into this topic by focusing on the real-life experiences of 10th graders at Samar National School as they go through their LAS paths. We can learn more about the "what" and "how" of how students connect with LAS thanks to phenomenology, which focuses on understanding each person's experience from their point of view (Creswell, 2014). Finding out what these events were really about can help the researchers understand how well LAS works as a learning tool in the specific setting of Samar National School. There is no doubt that LAS could be helpful. They give students a structure for learning on their own, encouraging them to be independent and self-directed (Chang, 2016). It is possible to get a better understanding of ideas through LAS by following clear directions and building up difficult tasks (Denicolo & Roth, 2015). Also, well-designed LAS can work with a variety of learning styles and provide a flexible way to learn that meets each person's needs (Duncan-Andrade & Thorne, 2017).

On the other hand, the LAS environment does have some problems. Some people are worried that too-structured formats or directions that aren't clear could make students frustrated and confused (McDrury & Boulton, 2019). Some LAS also have a one-size-fits-all method that might not take into account each student's unique learning style and needs (Han & Benson, 2018). If you rely too much on LAS, it could kill your creativity and stop you from doing inquiry-based learning, which is an important part of overall growth (van Manen, 2016).

This study wants to fill in that gap by going beyond just looking at finished tasks by exploring the phenomenological experiences of students at Samar National School with LAS. We want to know "how" students are engaged and find out what makes them more motivated to learn. In the same way, finding out "what" makes students angry can help Samar National School improve how LAS is designed and taught. The study's results can help with the creation and use of LAS in English language classes, especially in area public high schools. The study also fits with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 of the United Nations, which says that everyone should be able to get a good education and that everyone should be able to keep learning throughout their lives.

The main goal of this study is to help create a learning environment where LAS are not just finished tasks but also active tools that give Grade 10 students at Samar National School the power to effectively navigate their learning paths.

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive phenomenological method was used in this qualitative study to look into what it was like to use Learner's Activity Sheets (LAS) in English 10 lessons at Samar National School. The purpose of the study is to find out how 10th graders liked using LAS to improve their language skills and ability to think critically. Another goal of the study is to find out what problems and benefits come with using LAS in English 10 classes.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Samar National School, Catbalogan City, Samar under the Department of Education Catbalogan City Division.

Research Participants

Students in 10th grade at Samar National School were purposefully chosen to take part in this study. The following factors were used to choose these students:

1. Students who have properly signed up to be in 10th grade at Samar National School for the 2023-2024 school year
2. Students who have a general average of 80 are considered good.
3. Students who get an average of 80 or less in English.

The students who took part were picked to be a good representation of all the students who had used LAS to help them learn. Twenty-four students were asked for this study, but after fifteen people, the data was full. When adding more people to a study does not lead to more new ideas and information, this is called saturation. At this point, the process of gathering data no longer gives us any new or useful information.

Data Gathering Procedure

The Grade 10 students were interviewed in-depth as part of the data collection process. The purpose of these interviews was to learn more about the students' experiences using LAS. Because the interviews were semi-structured, both the students' free expression of ideas and sentiments and the researchers' ability to delve deeper into particular subjects were enabled.

A thematic analysis of the interview transcripts was part of the data analysis process. This required looking for patterns and themes in the data, classifying them, and examining how these themes related to one another. Before the transcription, written interviews were reviewed numerous times to collect and analyze the data. Colaizzi's phenomenological descriptive method was used as the model for the data analysis (Alzayani, 2015).

Ethical Considerations

The proposed phenomenological study on the experiences of using Learner's Activity Sheets (LAS) in English 10 classrooms at Samar National School adheres to the following ethical principles:

1. **Informed Consent:** The researchers must obtain informed consent from the grade 10 students participating in the study. This includes explaining the purpose of the study, the data collection methods, and the potential risks and benefits. Participants should be made aware that their participation is voluntary and they can withdraw at any time.
2. **Confidentiality and Privacy:** The researchers must ensure the confidentiality and privacy of the participants. Any personal or identifying information collected during the interviews should be kept secure and only used for the study. Participants should be assured that their responses will be anonymized in any reporting or publication.
3. **Minimizing Harm:** The researchers should take steps to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to the participants. The interview questions should be designed sensitively to avoid causing undue distress or anxiety.

Results and Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the experiences of Samar National School Grade 10 students who used Learners Activity Sheets (LAS) as part of their educational process. Improved Learning Outcomes and Student Limitations and Challenges were the study's two main themes. The study's findings offer insightful information about the difficulties students encountered when utilizing this cutting-edge teaching strategy as well as how well LAS can improve student learning outcomes.

Theme 1: Improved Learning Outcomes

Students in grade 10 at Samar National School saw a notable improvement in their learning outcomes as a result of the use of Learners Activity Sheets (LAS). Pupils' English language proficiency increased significantly, as evidenced by their enhanced communication and understanding abilities. Additionally, LAS promoted a lively learning environment by raising student involvement and participation in class activities. Active participation in conversations, arguments, and group projects, which encouraged cooperative learning and a feeling of community, were characteristics of this engagement. Additionally, LAS assisted students in strengthening their critical thinking abilities, which improved their capacity for efficient information analysis and decision-making. Overall, using LAS enhanced learning outcomes, demonstrating how well it works to support student learning and achievement.

Subtheme 1.1: Unlocking Academic Success

Students' English language ability increased significantly, exhibiting notable advancements in their linguistic abilities. Learners Activity Sheets (LAS) were introduced at Samar National School, and as a result, grade 10 students' English skills significantly improved. Pupils' language proficiency significantly improved, as evidenced by their improved communication and comprehension capabilities. Their comprehension of intricate materials, their ability to express themselves clearly, and their participation in insightful conversations all showed signs of development. Students were able to break through language hurdles, gain self-assurance in their language abilities, and realize their full academic potential because of LAS.

(1) *"It enhanced my capacity to arrange data, including recognizing a text's primary idea and illustrative details."*

(2) *"The English subject particularly benefits from the efficient use of LAS for transcoding text from linear to non-linear and vice versa. The LAS gave me enough details and had a clear conversation, which improved my comprehension."*

Subtheme 1.2: Engaging Minds

LAS promoted a more dynamic learning environment by increasing student participation and interest in class activities. At Samar National School, the use of Learners Activity Sheets (LAS) enhanced student involvement and participation in class activities, resulting in a more dynamic and interactive learning environment. Pupils were more likely to actively engage in group projects and debates, which promoted collaborative learning and a feeling of

community. Students' excitement, inventiveness, and critical thinking were evident during this interaction as they investigated difficult subjects and gained a greater comprehension of the material.

As per the statement made by a student participant:

(1) "LAS helped me discover that I can work on my own and with my classmates. With this habit, this helped us easily learn our worksheet and participate in class discussions not only in English but also in other subjects."

Subtheme 1.3 Critical Thinking Unleashed

Students gained critical thinking abilities through LAS, which improved their ability to evaluate data and make defensible conclusions. Students at Samar National School were able to improve their critical thinking abilities through the use of Learners Activity Sheets (LAS), which gave them the ability to examine material more efficiently and make wise decisions. By using LAS, students were able to get a deeper grasp of difficult subjects by learning how to assess the evidence, recognize patterns, and make logical conclusions. Their abilities to solve issues, think creatively, and face challenges with confidence were all results of their critical thinking. Through LAS, students gained the ability to successfully navigate the 21st century's difficulties, better preparing them for their future academic and professional endeavors.

According to the students who took part:

"Some words are difficult but when used in sentences, it becomes easy to understand and then I can think on my own ideas based on the sample sentences and use it daily."

"With LAS, I can now learn (myself) independently and able to learn at home."

Theme 2: Limitations and Challenges Experienced by Students

For students at Samar National School, using Learners Activity Sheets (LAS) came with several restrictions and difficulties. The need for pupils to adjust to a new teaching strategy that called for critical and creative thinking was one of the main obstacles. Students also had trouble efficiently managing their time because LAS required them to work alone and establish their deadlines. Additionally, a few students encountered difficulties with the technological features of LAS, such as using the online interface and turning in assignments. Notwithstanding these difficulties, students stated that LAS assisted them in gaining useful abilities including problem-solving, critical thinking, and time management.

Subtheme 2.1: Time Balancing Conundrums

Samar National School students found it difficult to use Learners Activity Sheets (LAS) to efficiently manage their time. Due to LAS's flexibility, which lets students work at their own pace, students occasionally had trouble setting priorities and sticking to deadlines. Pupils expressed feeling overburdened by the sheer amount of homework and the requirement to manage several projects at once. Some students turned in assignments late or did not meet expectations because they lacked time management skills. However, with direction and encouragement, students

were able to improve their time management abilities, which enabled them to stay on course and meet their objectives.

As stated by one of the student-participants:

(1) "Yes, one of the challenges I have faced while using LAS is on time-management. Since we are given LAS in all subjects, sometimes I struggle on prioritizing which LAS to answer first. This leads to cramming and failure in meeting deadlines."

Subtheme 2.2: Difficulty in Understanding

Students have trouble comprehending the LAS criteria and directions. Learners at Samar National School encountered difficulties comprehending the guidelines and specifications of Learners Activity Sheets (LAS). Students had to swiftly adjust to the new learning format when they were moved from traditional teaching methods to a more self-directed instruction style. Some students experienced bewilderment and frustration as a result of their inability to understand the standards and directives stated in the LAS. The absence of in-person interactions with teachers made it more difficult for students to learn because they were unable to ask questions or get answers to any problems they had right away. However, with the help of their friends and teachers, students overcame these obstacles and improved their comprehension of the LAS criteria.

As commented by the student-participants:

(1) "The instructions of some of the activities in the LAS are difficult to understand because of the words used in giving the instructions"

(2) "Yes, there are lessons which need to be clarified it would take time to ask and wait for the response of my teacher and internet is not available sometimes."

Subtheme 2.3: Limited Resources

Inadequate facilities and resources made it difficult to deploy LAS effectively. Limited facilities and resources made it difficult for Samar National School to implement Learners Activity Sheets (LAS). It was challenging for pupils to access the online platform and finish homework because of the school's antiquated equipment and lack of internet access. Students also had to share resources due to the restricted number of computers and printers available, which frequently caused delays and inefficiencies. It was difficult for the pupils to concentrate and maintain their motivation because there was nowhere specifically for them to work on LAS. Despite these obstacles, educators and students came up with inventive solutions to adjust and use the resources at hand, guaranteeing that LAS use remained effective.

As mentioned by one of the student-participant:

(1) "Some of the Learner's Activity Sheet is given through messenger which makes it difficult to access if there is no internet connection."

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However, using LAS also came with several drawbacks and difficulties for the students. One of the main difficulties was getting the students to adjust to a new way of teaching that called for critical and creative thinking (Hativa, 2013). Since LAS required students to work autonomously and establish their deadlines, they also had trouble efficiently managing their time (Johnson & Johnson, 2009). Moreover, some students had trouble utilizing the online platform and turning in assignments due to technical difficulties with LAS (Boud & Garrick, 2007). Notwithstanding these difficulties, students stated that LAS assisted them in gaining useful abilities including problem-solving, critical thinking, and time management (Hativa, 2013).

Learner's Activity Sheets (LAS) are becoming a standard component of many educational programs, particularly in blended and self-directed learning settings. With the aid of these resources, students may grasp, practice, and apply academic concepts in an organized manner. To maximize their teaching tactics, educators must comprehend how students use these sheets and how it affects their learning.

Conclusion

Learner's Activity Sheets (LAS) were found to significantly increase learning outcomes for Grade 10 pupils at Samar National School based on a qualitative phenomenological investigation. The study emphasized the advantages and difficulties that the participants faced, as well as the positive and negative experiences. The development of critical thinking abilities, improved English proficiency, and higher student involvement and engagement are among the important findings. Students were able to break through linguistic hurdles, gain self-assurance, and realize their full academic potential thanks to LAS. It was also discovered that the learners' obstacles included limited resources, trouble understanding instructions, and time-balancing dilemmas.

Students' learning is greatly impacted by navigating the activity sheet experience. It strengthens knowledge, fosters critical thinking, encourages autonomy, and increases participation. Although there may be difficulties, particularly for kids who need additional support, there are a lot of advantages to use LAS in the classroom. Activity sheets can be a helpful tool in assisting students in achieving academic achievement and preparing for lifelong learning when they are created well and used in conjunction with supportive teaching techniques.

Recommendations

The results of the study showed that LAS greatly enhanced students' critical thinking abilities, language competency, and general involvement in the learning process. Students were given more opportunities to participate actively in their education and succeed academically by LAS by creating a more lively and collaborative learning atmosphere in the classroom. In order to optimize the effectiveness of this approach, the school should offer thorough teacher preparation and guarantee the availability of required materials, look into strategies to overcome obstacles and constraints related to LAS implementation, like making sure teachers have enough resources and training. In order to support holistic academic development, conduct additional study to determine the long-term effects of LAS on student learning results and investigate ways to apply this strategy in other subject areas.

References

- Akhtar, K., & Thomson, J. A. (2017). A phenomenological study of entrepreneurial leadership in a family business setting. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 32(3), 344-359.
- Alzayani, S. (2015). The lived experiences of students with disabilities in Bahrain's higher education system: A phenomenological study. *Disability & Society*, 30(4), 595-613.
- Chang, N. (2016). Rethinking problem-based learning: From the lens of the cognitive load theory. *Innovation in Education and Teaching International*, 53(4), 398-408.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach (4th ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Denicolo, P., & Roth, W. M. (2015). Developing constructivist early childhood education research. *Early Child Development and Care*, 185(8), 1235-1248.
- Duncan-Andrade, J. M., & Thorne, A. (2017). Classroom matter: Engaged pedagogy in a neoliberal era. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 68(1), 28-44.
- Giorgi, A. (2009). *The descriptive phenomenological method in psychology: A modified Husserlian approach*. Pittsburgh, PA: Duquesne University Press.
- Han, J., & Benson, A. (2018). Promoting student autonomy through learner-centered instructional practices. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 30(2), 175-188.
- McDrury, J., & Boulton, C. (2019). Engaging students in active learning: Critical reflection on practice. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 38(1), 77-91.
- Merriam, S. B. (2020). *Qualitative research in practice: Examples for discussion and analysis*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- van Manen, M. (2016). *Phenomenology of practice: Meaning-giving methods in phenomenological research and writing*. New York, NY: Routledge.